
Analysis of Teaching Modules Based on Pancasila Student Profiles in Citizenship Education Subjects at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko

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ABSTRACT: This research aims to analyze teaching modules based on strengthening the Pancasila student profile in order to support the implementation of the Independent Curriculum in Indonesia. This teaching module is designed to integrate Pancasila values into the learning process, so that it can form the character of students who are faithful, devoted to God Almighty, have noble character, global diversity, work together, be independent, reason critically and are creative. The method used in this research is qualitative descriptive analysis with a case study approach in several schools that have implemented teaching modules based on strengthening the Pancasila student profile. The results of the analysis show that this teaching module is effective in integrating Pancasila values into daily learning. Teachers who use this module report improvements in students' understanding and application of Pancasila values. In addition, students show positive development in cognitive, affective and psychomotor aspects. The challenges faced include limited resources and expanding teachers' understanding of the concept of the Pancasila student profile. However, with the right training and support, this teaching module has great potential to improve the quality of education in Indonesia. This research concludes that teaching modules based on strengthening the Pancasila student profile can be an effective tool in creating a young generation of Indonesians who are not only academically intelligent but also have strong character and are based on Pancasila values. Recommendations are provided for further development of this module and expansion of its application at various levels of education.

KEYWORDS: Teaching Module, Pancasila Student Profile, PPKn

INTRODUCTION

Education in Indonesia is currently facing big challenges in forming a young generation who not only excels in academics, but also has strong character and is based on national values. To answer these challenges, the Indonesian government has initiated various efforts, one of which is strengthening the profile of Pancasila students as reflected in the Merdeka Curriculum. The Pancasila student profile consists of six main dimensions, namely faith and devotion to God Almighty, noble character, global diversity, mutual cooperation, independence, critical reasoning and creativity. These dimensions are expected to be able to form students who are not only intellectually competent, but also have high moral and social integrity (Alanur et al., 2023) .

The development of teaching modules based on strengthening the Pancasila student profile is a strategic step in realizing the vision of holistic and inclusive national education. This teaching module is designed to integrate Pancasila values into every aspect of learning, so that students can understand and apply these values in everyday life. The Independent Curriculum provides schools and teachers with the freedom to develop learning methods that are innovative and relevant to student needs and community dynamics. In the context of implementing teaching modules based on strengthening the Pancasila student profile, there are several basic questions that need to be answered:

1. How effective is this teaching module in integrating Pancasila values into learning?
2. What are the challenges faced by teachers and schools in implementing this teaching module?

This research aims to analyze the effectiveness and challenges of implementing teaching modules based on strengthening Pancasila student profiles in several schools. Specifically, this research aims to:

1. Assess the extent to which this teaching module can integrate Pancasila values into the learning process.
2. Identify the obstacles and obstacles faced in implementing the teaching module.

Based on the problems above, it is hoped that it will make a real contribution to the development of character education in Indonesia. By understanding the effectiveness and challenges of teaching modules based on strengthening the Pancasila student profile, education stakeholders can formulate more effective policies and strategies to strengthen character education (Rahimah, 2022).

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Apart from that, it is also hoped that this research can provide practical recommendations for teachers and schools in implementing teaching modules that are in accordance with Pancasila values.

METHODOLOGY

This study used descriptive qualitative method. Data was collected through observation, interviews and document analysis at several schools that have implemented teaching modules based on strengthening Pancasila student profiles. Data analysis was carried out qualitatively to identify patterns, themes and relationships between the variables studied (Siloto, 2023).

1. Class Observation

Observations were carried out to see directly how teaching modules based on strengthening the Pancasila student profile were implemented in the classroom. Researchers observed interactions between teachers and students, the teaching methods used, and students' responses to the material being taught. This observation helps in understanding the dynamics of learning and implementing Pancasila values in real contexts (Amus et al., 2024).

2. In-depth Interview

In-depth interviews were conducted with various parties involved in implementing this teaching module, including teachers, students and school principals. The interview aims to explore their perspectives regarding the effectiveness of the module, the challenges faced, and the impact felt. Interview questions were prepared in an open manner to allow respondents to provide in-depth and comprehensive answers (Sukmawati et al., 2024).

3. Document Analysis

The documents analyzed include learning implementation plans (RPP), syllabus, and teaching modules used by teachers. Document analysis aims to understand how Pancasila values are integrated into the curriculum and teaching materials. Apart from that, researchers also reviewed reports and records of student learning outcomes to see the influence of teaching modules on the development of their character and competencies (Lukman Nadjamuddin1 et al., 2024).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The teacher developed an independent curriculum teaching module in learning Pancasila Education in class VII A

Teachers before carrying out the learning process in the classroom, of course they have studied and prepared the material that they will convey to students which is developed in the independent curriculum teaching module and as much as possible the teacher designs a lesson that is as interesting as possible so that students in participating in the learning process are more active and purposeful. Learning can be achieved according to what is desired (Sunaryati et al., 2022).

Based on the results of observations on February 23 2024 carried out by researchers in class VII A where before teaching the teacher had prepared teaching modules that were appropriate to the material that would be delivered to students in accordance with the conditions and needs of the school.

Before developing a teaching module, a teacher must be able to master the material that will be presented to students so that the learning process runs well. As the results of interviews conducted by researchers with Mrs. F as a PPKn teacher in class VII A at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko regarding what difficulties mothers encountered in the process of preparing teaching modules.

"The process of compiling teaching modules has difficulties faced by every teacher, namely regarding the components in the teaching module and significant changes in assessment with the RPP which are often experienced by every teacher." (Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs. NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation:

"As a teacher, I still don't understand the teaching module compilers, where in the preparation process there are difficulties and also limited teacher references in the teaching module preparation process."

(Interview March 10, 2024)

Then the researchers asked how the results of students' achievements were different when using the previous curriculum and the independent curriculum. The following is an explanation from Mrs. F regarding this question:

"The difference in student achievement in the independent curriculum lies in the development of student character and morals, whereas in the previous curriculum the achievement lies in students' general academic abilities."

(Interview dated February 24, 2024)

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These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs. NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation:

"According to you, the difference between the previous curriculums lies in the focus and general academic abilities of students, while the independent curriculum focuses on students' academic and moral abilities."

(Interview dated March 10, 2024)

Then the researcher asked what preparations the mother made in implementing the independent curriculum teaching module. The following is an explanation from Mrs. F regarding this question:

"Preparations are made before implementing teaching modules, of course we as teachers must first analyze learning outcomes, develop teaching modules, and adapt learning to characteristic stages."

(Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results were also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs. NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation:

"Mature teacher preparation in implementing the independent curriculum has several parts, including learning that involves understanding the principles, training and professional development." (Interview dated March 10, 2024)

Then the researcher asked what steps the mother took in compiling the teaching module. The following is an explanation from Mrs. F regarding this question:

"As for the steps in compiling teaching modules, of course we as teachers must determine learning objectives, determine learning content and design the structure of teaching modules so that the learning process runs well in accordance with what has been created."

(Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs. NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation:

"The procedure for preparing teaching modules starts from analyzing the needs of teachers, students and schools. Identify the dimensions of the Pancasila student profile that will be developed, determine the flow of learning objectives."

(Interview March 10, 2024)

Then the researcher asked how the mother adjusted the steps and needs of each student. The following is an explanation from Mrs. F regarding this question:

"Of course, in adjusting the steps and needs of each student, of course we as teachers must first implement differentiated lessons which are done through content, processes or products."

(Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs. NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation:

"Of course we have to adapt the existing facilities and infrastructure at school so that what we are going to convey can be implemented and understood by students." (Interview March 10, 2024)

Then the researchers asked students at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko whether you know what an independent curriculum teaching module is. The following are the results of an interview with NH

In my opinion, the Independent Curriculum teaching module is a substitute for RPP which has a varied format and includes learning material/content, learning methods, interpretation and evaluation techniques which are prepared systematically and impressively to achieve the expected indicators of success.

Researchers also asked class VII students AN with the following interview results.

In my opinion, the teaching module in the independent curriculum is a learning unit regulated in the laws in force in Indonesia, if the previous curriculum was called a syllabus (RPP).

Researchers also asked class VII students, namely RS with the following interview results.

In my opinion, the independent curriculum teaching module is a teaching tool used by teachers to design and implement learning activities in the classroom.

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Then the researcher asked what you did to develop the independent curriculum teaching module in learning Pancasila education. The following is an explanation from Mrs. F regarding this question:

"In developing independent curriculum teaching modules, of course we start by compiling modules, knowing strategies, developing teaching modules, preparing assessments, and fulfilling two minimum requirements, namely meeting existing criteria and learning activities in teaching modules in accordance with the principles of learning and assessment. (Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs. NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation:

"Of course, in developing teaching modules, we as teachers must first prepare the module, prepare assessments, develop the teaching module and fulfill two minimum requirements. What is meant by two minimum requirements are meeting existing criteria and learning activities in teaching modules in accordance with learning principles.

(Interview March 10, 2024)

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted by the researcher, the researcher concluded that before developing a teaching module, the teacher must first prepare the module, know the strategy, develop the teaching module, prepare an assessment, and fulfill two minimum requirements, namely meeting existing criteria and learning activities in the teaching module according to with the principles of learning and assessment. Apart from that, in adjusting the educational needs of the teacher, the teacher adjusts the existing facilities and infrastructure at the school so that what will be delivered can be implemented and understood by the students (Salsabilla et al., 2023).

Does the teacher implement the independent curriculum teaching module in learning Pancasila education in class VII A?

Success in the learning process in the classroom is not only influenced by the quality and skills of the teacher, but there are several components that support the learning process, one of which is how the teacher implements the independent curriculum teaching modules in the classroom. The PPKn teacher at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko has carried out activities that can support the growth of students' skills during the learning process, where the teacher always motivates students so that students are enthusiastic about participating in learning in the classroom. As the results of interviews conducted by researchers with Mrs. F as a PPKn teacher at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko regarding what obstacles she faced when implementing the independent curriculum teaching module. The following is the explanation:

"In implementing teaching modules, the obstacle faced by every teacher is the lack of teacher understanding and preparation in the process of implementing teaching modules."

(Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs. NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation:

"The obstacles we face in implementing the independent curriculum teaching modules are a lack of understanding regarding the essence of the curriculum and a lack of facilities and infrastructure."

(Interview March 10, 2024)

Then the researchers asked students at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko about the differences between the independent curriculum and the previous curriculum. The following are the results of an interview NH

In my opinion, the independent curriculum provides more freedom and flexibility for students and focuses on developing students' character and morals, whereas the previous curriculum only focused on students' academic abilities.

Researchers also asked class VII students A with the following interview results.

Our view as students and what I feel now is that in the independent curriculum I am free to choose what I want according to my characteristics without being burdened at all, whereas in the previous curriculum (K13) I felt burdened because I had to achieve the KKM targets that had been targeted by the teacher so that we less comfortable with the previous curriculum.

Researchers also asked class VII students, namely RS with the following interview results.

In my opinion, the independent curriculum provides more freedom, flexibility and focuses on developing students' character and morals, whereas the previous curriculum was more focused on academic abilities which had to achieve the targeted KKM targets.

Then the researchers asked students at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko whether by implementing the independent curriculum teaching modules it was easy for you to understand the lessons. The following are the results of an interview with NH and NF

In my opinion, so far I can still understand the independent curriculum with its various teaching methods and techniques in providing or delivering material.

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Researchers also asked class VIII students A with the following interview results.

Yes, I really understand because in the independent curriculum learning is organized, so we as students when studying do not feel confused because we are required before the learning process takes place we already know the basic essence of the lesson.

Researchers also asked class VIII students, namely RS with the following interview results.

While implementing the independent curriculum, I was still adapting so that I could understand the independent curriculum with its various teaching methods and ways of providing the material so that it could reach me because it was quite difficult for me to understand quickly.

Then the researcher asked the mother whether the independent curriculum could continue to be implemented on an ongoing basis. The following is an explanation from Mrs. F regarding this question:

"The independent curriculum can continue to be implemented on an ongoing basis through fundamental regulations in accordance with school and government policies." (Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation:

"The independent curriculum can of course be continued depending on government policy and public support which determines the continuation of the curriculum." (Interview March 10, 2024)

Then the researchers asked students at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko about whether the objectives of the independent curriculum had been achieved during the learning process. The following are the results of an interview with NH and NF. Yes, this has been achieved because at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko, student learning can improve starting from learning motivation, competency development, and improving student character. So in my opinion it has achieved the aim of the independent curriculum.

Researchers also asked class VII students A with the following interview results.

Yes, it has been achieved because the independent curriculum is now simpler and deeper and focuses on material and developing student competencies which makes the learning process fun and not rushed.

Researchers also asked class VII students, namely RS with the following interview results.

In my opinion, this has been achieved because in the learning process, as a student, I felt an increase in motivation, character improvement and competency development, which made me more enthusiastic about participating in the learning process in the classroom.

Then the researchers asked students at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko about whether by implementing the teaching module you were active in the learning process. The following are the results of an interview with NH:

Yes, very active because in the independent curriculum we are required to be active in our respective fields.

Researchers also asked class VII students A with the following interview results.

Yes, I personally am quite active in understanding the material that has been given, as well as implementing it during the learning process.

Researchers also asked class VII students, namely RS with the following interview results.

Personally, I am not very active because, as in the beginning, I have not been able to quickly understand the material that has been given and am not able to implement it at this time.

Then the researcher asked what factors hindered the implementation of the independent curriculum teaching module. The following is an explanation from Mrs. F regarding this question:

"There are two inhibiting factors in implementing the independent curriculum teaching module, namely the first, internal factors include (motivation, student attitudes and student interests, talents) while external factors include (parental support)."

(Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs. NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation:

"As I said earlier, the factor that is hampering the implementation of independent curriculum teaching modules is the lack of facilities and infrastructure in schools."

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(Interview March 10, 2024)

Then the researchers asked students at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko about what challenges you faced during the implementation of the independent curriculum at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following are the results of an interview NH:

In my opinion, Sis, the challenge I faced during the implementation of the independent curriculum at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko was difficulties during the lessons because it was difficult to adapt to the characteristics of the independent curriculum.

Researchers also asked class VII students AN and BA with the following interview results.

If the challenge is quite mental and you have to be able to use ACT where all the assignments given by the teacher are all through ACT operations, whether in the form of making Google videos, Canva and others. Apart from that, students are required to be more active in their respective fields during the learning process.

Researchers also asked class VII students, namely RS with the following interview results.

In my opinion, the challenges I faced during the implementation of the independent curriculum at school were difficulties during the learning process because it was difficult to adapt to the characteristics of the independent curriculum and difficulties in carrying out assignments.

Then the researchers asked students at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko about whether there had been any changes to lesson hours with the independent curriculum. The following are the results of an interview with NH:

If there is a change in time, it is because in the previous curriculum there was no P5 (Pancasila student profile) learning, now there is a Pancasila student profile for two hours per day and also the learning time which used to be 3 (three) hours has become 2 (two) hours, now 4 (hours) has become 3 (hours) and then the time to go home has also been reduced from 02:45 now to 01:45 every day.

Researchers also asked class VII students AN and BA with the following interview results.

In my opinion, there is no change in learning hours, only differences in teaching methods and models.

Researchers also asked class VII students, namely R with the following interview results.

Regarding lesson hours, it seems that there are no permanent changes to the previous curriculum.

Then the researcher asked what mothers thought were the considerations in designing and developing an independent curriculum teaching module. The following is an explanation from Mrs. F regarding this question:

"In designing and developing a teaching module, of course we must consider the stage of development and level of achievement of students according to their needs and characteristics."

(Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs. NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation:

"In designing and developing teaching modules, of course we must determine learning objectives by understanding the targets that students want to achieve, and teachers can prepare appropriate and useful material."

(Interview dated February 24, 2024)

Then the researchers asked students at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko about whether the teacher gave you directions or solutions to overcome the problems you faced. The following are the results of an interview with

In my opinion, during the learning process the teacher always provides very good solutions and suggestions so that we as students feel happy when following the learning process and don't feel nervous when asking questions.

Researchers also asked class VII students AN and BA with the following interview results.

During the learning process, when the teacher asked about the material that had been presented, we responded well, but what we had said was wrong, but the teacher always provided solutions and directions so that we understood what the question meant.

Researchers also asked class VII students, namely R with the following interview results.

In my opinion, the teachers here really care about their students, starting from giving directions before learning, providing very good solutions and suggestions so that we students can follow the learning well.

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Then the researchers asked students at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko about what learning resources teachers used during the learning process. The following are the results of an interview with NH and NF

So, Sis, the learning resources used during the learning process include textbooks, LKS (student worksheets), market days and so on.

Researchers also asked class VII students AN and BA with the following interview results.

The learning resources used by students are LKS (student worksheets), cellphones, textbooks, market days and so on.

Researchers also asked class VII students, namely R with the following interview results.

In my opinion, so far the learning sources used are textbooks, LKS (student worksheet), Google, market day and so on.

Then the researcher asked the mother whether this curriculum structure had an impact on teachers' teaching hours. The following is an explanation from Mrs. F regarding this question:

"There is no impact of change because the total lesson hours for each subject are allocated for two hours of learning activities from the previous hour." (Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation from Mrs NH:

"There is no impact of change, it's just that we as teachers are given the challenge to arrange the learning schedule from the previous hour.

(Interview March 10, 2024)

Then the researchers asked students at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko about what difficulties you often face in the learning process.

The following are the results of an interview with NH class VII and NF

In my opinion, there are no difficulties as long as the independent curriculum is implemented, it's just that there are still some students who don't really understand the curriculum.

Researchers also asked class VII students A with the following interview results.

The difficulties faced in learning so far remain, it's just that it's difficult to adapt.

Researchers also asked class VII students, namely R with the following interview results.

In my opinion, the difficulties that students often face include difficulty understanding learning material, difficulty motivating themselves and so on.

Then the researcher asked how the mother implemented the independent curriculum teaching module in learning Pancasila education. The following is an explanation from Mrs. F regarding this question:

"In implementing teaching modules, we as teachers implement teaching modules according to the context, characteristics and needs of students and make adjustments to learning methods within."

(Interview dated February 24, 2024)

These results are also strengthened by the results of an interview with Mrs. NH as a PPKn teacher for class V of SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko. The following is the explanation from Mrs. NH:

"Of course, in implementing the independent curriculum teaching modules, we always adjust the context, characteristics and needs of students so that the learning process runs smoothly."

(Interview March 10, 2024)

Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted by researchers, the researchers concluded that in implementing teaching modules teachers must be able to understand and have preparation in the learning process so that the teaching and learning process runs well. There are several factors that hinder the implementation of teaching modules, namely internal factors and external factors.

DISCUSSION

Teachers develop independent curriculum teaching modules in Pancasila Education Learning at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko

In developing teaching modules, educators and educational units can use various strategies as long as the resulting teaching module meets the predetermined criteria and learning activities in the teaching module in accordance with the principles of learning and

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assessment. The criteria for independent curriculum teaching modules are as follows; (1) Essential, namely every subject has a concept through learning experiences and cross-disciplinary knowledge (Mulyani & Insani, 2023), (2) Interesting, meaningful and challenging, namely teachers can foster interest in students and include students actively in learning, related to cognitive and experience that he has so that it is not too complex and not too easy for his age (Mustika et al., 2023), (3) Relevant and contextual, namely relating to cognitive elements and experiences that have been previously owned and according to the conditions of the time and place where the student is, and (4) Continuous, namely that learning activities must be related to the student's learning phases (phase 1, phase 2, phase 3), (Goo et al., 2024).

The aim of developing teaching modules according to learning and assessment guidelines is to enrich learning tools that can guide teachers to carry out learning in closed and open classes (Jannah et al., 2022). In this case, the independent curriculum gives teachers the freedom to enrich modules in two ways, namely teachers can choose or modify teaching modules that have been prepared by the government and adapted to students' characters and arrange modules individually according to the material and students' characters (Salsabilla et al., 2023).

Based on research regarding Pancasila Education Teachers in developing independent curriculum teaching modules, before carrying out the learning process, teacher's first start by compiling modules, knowing strategies, developing teaching modules, preparing assessments and fulfilling two minimum requirements. What is meant by two minimum requirements are meeting existing criteria and learning activities in teaching modules in accordance with learning and assessment principles (Triana et al., 2023). Apart from that, the teacher has been able to develop teaching modules which can be seen from the modules that the teacher has prepared in accordance with the ministry's guidelines and how the teacher conveys material in the classroom, how the teacher provides opportunities for students, provides arguments regarding the learning that has been conveyed and how to provide response or feedback to students so that the learning process becomes interesting and students do not feel bored when taking part in learning (Alimuddin, 2023).

Apart from that, in developing teaching modules, the Independent Curriculum becomes a benchmark in developing modules so that what has been prepared can help students understand what we have conveyed to them both in terms of knowledge and skills.

The teacher implements the independent curriculum teaching module in learning Pancasila education in class VII A

Implementing independent curriculum teaching modules of course teachers have good strategies to ensure the learning process runs smoothly, therefore strategies in the world of education are very important and influential. In implementing teaching modules, teachers must of course try to make students more interested in the learning process so that learning occurs and in particular teachers must also frequently update learning so that learning is not just the same (Dewi & Suniasih, 2023).

One of the keys to success that determines the success of the independent curriculum analysis is the teacher, because the teacher is an important factor that has a big influence, and even really determines the success or failure of students in learning (Mulyasa, 2015). Ahmad Susanto (2013) said that teachers as the spearhead in the implementation of education are very influential parties in the learning process. The teacher's expertise and authority determines the continuity of the learning process in the classroom and its effects outside the classroom. Teachers must be good at bringing their students to the goals they want to achieve (Setiawan et al., 2022).

Based on research regarding Pancasila Education teachers in implementing the independent curriculum teaching module in Pancasila education learning at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko, in implementing the teaching module the teacher implemented the teaching module according to the context, characteristics and needs of students and made adjustments to learning methods in the classroom (Maulida, 2022). What is meant by context-appropriate teaching modules is that the material prepared in learning is appropriate to the students' real life situations or their surroundings. (Ardianti & Amalia, 2022) of course the application is different because each student has different characteristics, for example the abilities of students a and b do not have the same characteristics, so the way to provide understanding of the material is according to the students' own needs. Apart from that, the teacher is able to help students to understand the lesson well, where a teacher is said to be successful in teaching if the student has understood the lesson being taught so that the implementation of the independent curriculum teaching module is carried out as desired (Setiawan et al., 2022).

The steps that teachers prepare when implementing the module include (Marlina, 2023) :

1. Diagnostic assessment is an initial assessment to identify students' potential, characteristics, needs, developmental stages and stages of learning achievement. Assessments are generally carried out at the beginning of the learning year, so that the results can be used to carry out further planning regarding the learning methods that should be used.
2. Planning

Arranging the learning process according to the results of diagnostic assessments, as well as grouping students based on ability level.

1. Learning

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During the learning process, the teacher will conduct regular formative assessments, to determine student learning progress and make adjustments to learning methods, if necessary. At the end of the learning process, teachers can also carry out summative assessments as a process of evaluating the achievement of learning objectives (Rahimah, 2022)

Based on the implementation of the Independent Curriculum teaching module, its application in the classroom has been fulfilled, as can be seen from how teachers provide explanations to students, provide motivation to students and help students understand the learning material by approaching students so that students do not feel embarrassed to ask questions.

CONCLUSION

This research shows that teaching modules based on strengthening the Pancasila student profile are effective in integrating Pancasila values into learning and have a positive impact on the formation of student character and competence. However, the successful implementation of this module is highly dependent on adequate resource support, teacher training, and efforts to overcome existing challenges. With the right support, this teaching module has great potential to improve the quality of education in Indonesia and form a young generation with strong character and based on the values of Pancasila. Accompanied by the independent curriculum teaching module in learning Pancasila education in class VII A at SMP Negeri 2 Salomekko, the teacher starts by compiling the module, knowing the strategy for developing the teaching module, preparing an assessment, and must fulfill two minimum requirements, namely meeting existing criteria and activities. Learning in teaching modules is in accordance with the principles of learning and assessment. Apart from that, the modules that have been prepared by the teacher are in accordance with the ministry's guidelines as well as how the teacher conveys material in the classroom, how the teacher provides opportunities for students, provides arguments regarding the learning that has been conveyed and how the teacher provides responses or feedback to students, so that the process learning becomes interesting and not boring.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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